

8 Checking taxonomy for DOI assignation

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Introduction

The Global Information System (GLIS) of the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA) assigns Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (PGRFA).

Users wishing to assign DOIs to their collection can, among other means, use the Excel-based batch format described at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11274488> for *ex situ* conservation and at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15161723> for *in situ* conservation. In the following, the *ex situ* format will be used in the examples, but the examples will be easily applicable to the *in situ* format as well.

The purpose of this paper is to show how to use one of the tools made available by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), namely the "Species name matching", that can be accessed at <https://www.gbif.org/tools/species-lookup>. In this page, you can download two example files: `SIMPLEEXAMPLE.CSV` and `ADVANCEDEXAMPLE.CSV`. For our purpose, `SIMPLEEXAMPLE.CSV` is appropriate and will be used below.

When GLIS receives an Excel document containing the information to be used to assign DOIs, it scans the document one row at a time. Among other checks performed, the unicity of the triple Genus + Specific epithet + Accession Number is verified, within the document and among DOIs already assigned by the same registrant, to avoid assigning multiple DOIs to the same PGRFA. The use of the three pieces of information is required because some Gene banks assign Accession Numbers by collection, i.e. by Genus. Although rare, it is possible that the same Accession number is used within the same Gene bank, to identify PGRFA belonging to different genera.

The above check assumes that the taxonomy provided is correct. However, in some cases, it was found that typos in the genus or specific epithet led to two DOIs being assigned, one to the PGRFA with the correct taxonomy and another to the PGRFA with the incorrect taxonomy, even if the Accession Numbers are the same, effectively bypassing the validation checks. Additionally, ensuring that the taxonomy is correct, even if no duplicate DOI assignation is involved, is a good practice to improve data quality.

Preparing your Excel document to use with the GBIF tool

To check the taxonomy of the PGRFA you wish to assign DOIs to requires some simple preparation of the Excel table you are about to submit. If you obtained the Excel table from your documentation system, you may be able to obtain the properly formatted text file following the structure of `SIMPLEEXAMPLE.CSV`. This example file is structured as follows (in *italic* our comments):

scientificName, kingdom	<i>this is the title line, do not delete it</i>
puma concolor	<i>this is a sample line, no kingdom specified</i>
abies alba	<i>this is another sample line, no kingdom specified</i>

As you can see, the kingdom is optional and we will omit it in our examples, but leave ", kingdom" in the title line because it is required. The idea is to compile a text file with the title line and, each on a separate line, the scientific names (Genus + space + Specific epithet) we want to check. Of course, we need to enter only unique scientific names, the result of the check will be applicable to all PGRFA sharing the same scientific name.

For example, the content of our text file could be:

```
scientificName, kingdom      this is the title line exactly as in SIMPLEEXAMPLE.CSV
Oryza sativa                 genera can begin with an uppercase letter
Triticum aestivum           another scientificName with an error in the Genus
```

You can enter up to 3,000 names, which is more than enough in most cases. For large files, a simple technique will be shown below to submit only unique scientific names. It is possible to add subtaxa to the scientificName, e.g. "Triticum aestivum subsp. aestivum". Just make sure there is no comma in the scientificName and remove any authority name if present.

You can likely produce a suitable text file from your documentation system but, in case you have an Excel table to process, here is how you can prepare a file to submit to GBIF for checking. As an example, we will look at the *ex situ* format mentioned in the Introduction above.

The GLIS Excel table contains several columns, but the ones we are interested in are I (Genus), J (Specific epithet) and Q (Subtaxa). An example Excel table could then be (omitting the other columns):

	A	B	C
1	Genus	Species	Subtaxa
2	Phaseolus	vulgaris	var. vulgaris
3	Phaseolus	vulgaris	
4	Zea	mays	var. indentata
5	Zea	mays	
6	Arachis	villosa	
7	Arachis	velosa	
8	Cucurbita	pepo	
9	Zea	mays	
10	Completely	wrong	

Note that the second *Arachis* has a typo in the specific epithet. We also added a *Completely wrong* name to see what GBIF will tell us about it. We now need to add a new column D that will contain the juxtaposition of these three columns to form the scientificName we need. The formula, to put in the column at the right of Subtaxa is

= A2 & " " & B2 & IF(ISBLANK(C2); ""; " " & C2)

The formula combines columns A and B and, if not empty, adds column C too. You can easily adjust the formula to suit your Excel table. Repeat the formula for all the rows of the table obtaining the following table.

	A	B	C	D
1	Genus	Species	Subtaxa	Scientific Name
2	Phaseolus	vulgaris	var. vulgaris	Phaseolus vulgaris var. vulgaris
3	Phaseolus	vulgaris		Phaseolus vulgaris
4	Zea	mays	var. indentata	Zea mays var. indentata
5	Zea	mays		Zea mays
6	Arachis	villosa		Arachis villosa
7	Arachis	velosa		Arachis velosa
8	Cucurbita	pepo		Cucurbita pepo
9	Zea	mays		Zea mays
10	Completely	wrong		Completely wrong

The next step, if your list is very long, is to reduce the list of Scientific Names to just the unique values. Excel lets us easily to this by entering the following formula in the top cell next to the first Scientific Name (cell E2 in the example above):

= UNIQUE (D2:D10)

Where D2 and D10 will be the coordinates of the first and last cell of our Scientific Name column. The final table will be

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Genus	Species	Subtaxa	Scientific Name	scientificName,kingdom
2	Phaseolus	vulgaris	var. vulgaris	Phaseolus vulgaris var. vulgaris	Phaseolus vulgaris var. vulgaris
3	Phaseolus	vulgaris		Phaseolus vulgaris	Phaseolus vulgaris
4	Zea	mays	var. indentata	Zea mays var. indentata	Zea mays var. indentata
5	Zea	mays		Zea mays	Zea mays
6	Arachis	villosa		Arachis villosa	Arachis villosa
7	Arachis	velosa		Arachis velosa	Arachis velosa
8	Cucurbita	pepo		Cucurbita pepo	Cucurbita pepo
9	Zea	mays		Zea mays	Completely wrong
10	Completely	wrong		Completely wrong	Completely wrong

As you can see, in column E, only unique names appear. We just need now to copy the content of the column on the right (that we purposely titled with the line required by the GBIF tool), of course just the non-empty cells, and paste it into a text editor obtaining:

```
scientificName,kingdom
Phaseolus vulgaris var. vulgaris
Phaseolus vulgaris
Zea mays var. indentata
Zea mays
Arachis villosa
Arachis velosa
Cucurbita pepo
Completely wrong
```

Let's save this file as *taxacheck.txt* (but any name will do). We then open our web browser and go to <https://www.gbif.org/tools/species-lookup>. The following page (Figure 1) will appear where we can upload our file by clicking "SELECT FILE" or by dragging and dropping it on the grey circle.

Figure 1: GBIF Species name matching page

The file will be uploaded and its content will be displayed on the page as follows

Figure 2: Uploaded table page

We can optionally first click the "Plantae" icon to make sure the check is performed only against plant taxa and then click "MATCH TO GBIF BACKBONE" obtaining the result below

Figure 3: Results page

Let's now look at this page:

- the "EXACT" matches are obviously OK
- matches with "FUZZY" indicate that the name on the left, the one we entered, is not fully correct. The tool shows the closest match. We recommend that you consider updating your taxonomy to correct any mistakes. In case of synonyms, e.g. *Lycopersicon esculentum* and *Solanum lycopersicon*, the "HIGHERRANK" matchType may appear showing that your taxonomy might require updating

- when "NONE" appears, your taxonomy cannot be matched, even remotely. Please take corrective action

If you click "GENERATE CSV" you will be able to download a CSV file with additional information on the results.

If any of the results is not marked as "EXACT", it is important that you carefully check the CSV file and determine if your taxonomy needs to be modified. In this case, please make sure that you apply the correction to your documentation system and export the table again before sending it to us for DOI assignation. This is because, if you push the incorrect taxonomy to Genesys or later export another Excel table for GLIS, it will cause the incorrect taxonomy to propagate to GLIS.